

The potential of extended reality for studying interoception in functional neurological disorders

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Abstract

Functional neurological disorder (FND) is a common cause of neurological symptoms that can be severe and chronic but the aetiology is poorly understood. Contemporary theories have moved away from simplistic psychological models and propose mechanisms involving altered bodily awareness, agency, and emotion regulation, potentially arising from disrupted interoceptive processing and maladaptive predictive brain mechanisms. Extended reality (XR) technologies, including virtual, augmented and mixed reality, offer a unique platform to study and modulate these processes by transforming internal bodily signals into perceptible, interactive feedback. This review synthesizes current evidence on interoception in FND and XR-based interventions in healthy and clinical populations, highlighting how XR can experimentally manipulate mind-body interactions through visuo-interoceptive synchrony, biofeedback, and embodied avatars. Despite evidence supporting their clinical potential, the effects of XR paradigms on interoception in FND have yet to be explored. Mechanistic and therapeutic research directions are proposed, including XR-based interoceptive assessment, gamified biofeedback, haptic heartbeat training, and integration with physiotherapy to amplify interoceptive signals. XR thus provides both a mechanistic tool to probe disrupted interoception and a novel therapeutic medium to recalibrate bodily self-awareness and agency. Future studies should evaluate feasibility, safety, and clinical efficacy, with attention to the multidimensional nature of interoception and individual variability in FND presentations.

Introduction

This paper is a narrative review of the methods that have been developed to study interoception in extended reality (XR), with the potential to be used in mechanistic studies of FND and potentially also therapeutically. We start by outlining the basics of what FND is and briefly reviewing its complexities before then giving an overview of what interoception is and how it is tested or assessed. We then review what paradigms for its measurement or study have been developed for 'extended reality' and what this is. To conclude we discuss how such methods could be applied to FND and their differing utility.

Functional Neurological Disorder

Functional neurological disorder (FND) refers to neurological symptoms arising from changes in brain function rather than structure and defined on the basis of 'positive' clinical features that distinguish it from other disorders that reflect an underlying pathology that is not consistent with, or even explainable by, structural lesions (National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke, 2025). FND encompasses a range of presentations that mimic structural neurological conditions, including functional motor disorder (FMD), functional seizures (FS), functional visual symptoms (FVS), persistent postural-perceptual dizziness (PPPD), functional tremor, weakness, and myoclonus (Stone, 2025). FND is the second most common reason for referral to a neurologist, after headache (Stone et al., 2010).

FND symptoms typically emerge in adolescence or adulthood, often following psychological stress, physical injury, or illness (Espay et al., 2018). Based on patient reports, its etiology is multifactorial, reflecting an interplay of biological, psychological, and social factors (Millman et al., 2024). Despite advances, the precise mechanisms by which symptoms arise remain poorly understood. Epidemiological data suggest that stressful or traumatic life events may act as triggers, producing maladaptive escape or freezing responses (Nicholson et al., 2016). However, causal relationships between such stressors and symptom onset remain unproven.

Historically, FND was labelled "hysteria," reflecting misogynistic and unscientific interpretations dating back thousands of years (Raynor & Baslet, 2021). In the late 19th century, the neurologist Jean-Martin Charcot reframed hysteria as a partly hereditary disorder of the nervous system rather than a uterine or purely psychological condition and investigated the role of suggestion and autosuggestion in symptom generation (Raynor & Baslet, 2021). Subsequently, Freud and Breuer reframed it as conversion disorder, suggesting that repressed emotion could "convert" into bodily symptoms (Feinstein & Voon, 2021). By the late 20th and early 21st centuries, the diagnosis was redefined as functional neurological disorder, characterized by positive 'rule-in' clinical signs (eg. Hoover's sign, tremor entrainment test, tuning fork test) (Stone et al., 2020). In parallel, advances in neuroimaging and cognitive neuroscience provided mechanistic models linking altered brain network function from 'computational errors' at the level of the 'predictive coding or processing' of symptoms (Edwards et al., 2012).

Current treatments include psychoeducation, specialist physiotherapy and psychological therapies such as specialist cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT), and multidisciplinary treatment. (Stone et al., 2016). Also, active research is being conducted into many other treatments such as other types of psychological therapy (e.g. Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT), mindfulness and group therapy) (Graham & Kemp, 2018) (Myers et al., 2021), Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation (TMS) (for motor or visual symptoms) (Pick et al., 2020; Grande et al., 2021) and more recently Eye Movement Desensitization and Reprocessing (EMDR) (Cope et al., 2021), psychedelics (Butler et al., 2020) as well as BCI (Morris et al., 2025).

Predictive Processing Theory and FND

A leading explanatory framework is predictive processing, which conceptualises the brain as a hierarchical inference system that continuously generates predictions about sensory input and updates them based on prediction errors (Friston, 2012). In FND, pathological priors - high-level predictions about bodily states - may become overweighted, dominating incoming sensory evidence and leading to the perception and experience of symptoms despite intact neural structures (Edwards et al., 2012).

This model helps explain several key findings in FND:

- Attention: Directing attention away from symptoms often reduces their severity, consistent with attention reinforcing high-level priors (Edwards & Bhatia, 2012).
- Sense of agency: Impaired agency in FND may arise when predicted and actual outcomes fail to align, creating a mismatch between low- and high-level predictions (Edwards et al., 2012).
- Interoception: Altered internal bodily awareness could underlie these processes by disrupting how the brain generates and updates bodily predictions (Drane et al., 2021).

Interoception

Interoception: the sensing, interpretation, and integration of internal bodily signals, has become increasingly recognized as a key mechanism in FND. Interoception is understood as a multimodal construct comprising accuracy (objective awareness of internal bodily processes), insight (self-perceived confidence in one's accuracy), and sensibility (subjective ratings of how attuned or responsive one feels to bodily sensations) (Millman et al., 2023). Disturbances in interoceptive processing may contribute to the disorder's hallmark symptoms by disrupting predictive models of bodily state, action, and emotion (Seth, 2013; Edwards et al., 2012). Patients with FND often report feeling detached from their bodies or unable to trust bodily sensations and inducing dissociation has been found to decrease interoceptive accuracy (Pick et al., 2020). At the same time though, patients with FND often show heightened self-reported

interoceptive sensibility despite reduced interoceptive accuracy, indicating a mismatch between objective and subjective bodily awareness (Koreki et al., 2020). These insights position interoception as both a potential mechanism and therapeutic target in FND, complementing cognitive and sensorimotor models. Additionally, alexithymia, or difficulty identifying and describing emotions, is elevated in FND (Van Dijk et al., 2024). This trait may reflect a deficit in higher-order interoceptive integration, where emotional meaning fails to emerge from bodily states, reinforcing misattribution of sensations and the development of functional symptoms.

Neural Correlates of FND

Functional neurological disorder (FND) is associated with alterations in several large-scale brain networks involved in motor control, emotion regulation, self-agency, and interoception. Neuroimaging evidence increasingly supports FND as a multi-network disorder involving abnormal interactions between limbic/salience, sensorimotor, and self-agency networks (Perez et al., 2021). Across structural and functional imaging studies, patients commonly show heightened amygdala and insula connectivity with motor control networks, alongside altered connectivity of the temporoparietal junction (TPJ) and prefrontal regions implicated in self-agency. Such findings suggest excessive emotional influence on motor behavior and disrupted integration of sensorimotor predictions, though replication remains limited and cohort heterogeneity is high (Perez et al., 2021).

Aybek et al. (2013) used fMRI to examine individuals with FND recalling autobiographical events of high “escape” relevance compared to healthy controls. They found increased activity in the left dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (DLPFC) and decreased activity in the left hippocampus, suggesting mechanisms of memory suppression. Additionally, right supplementary motor area (SMA) and TPJ activity were increased, while patients failed to activate the right inferior frontal cortex (rIFC) in both conditions (Aybek et al., 2013). Functional connectivity between the amygdala and motor regions (SMA and cerebellum) was also enhanced (Aybek et al., 2013). These findings suggest abnormal interactions between emotion, memory, and motor networks in FND, although such correlates do not yet constitute statistically robust biomarkers for diagnosis.

The TPJ, a key region for body ownership and agency, shows altered activation in FND and may underlie patients’ disrupted sense of body self-awareness (Aybek et al., 2013). Altered TPJ function could therefore contribute to reduced interoceptive trust - the subjective sense of being “at home” in one’s body - and to the loss of agency often reported in functional motor symptoms (Millman et al., 2023).

The insula, especially its mid and anterior subdivisions, is central to interoceptive awareness. Interoceptive attention has been shown to activate the dorsal mid-insula as well as the ventral and anterior insula clusters (Simmons et al., 2012). Similarly, heartbeat monitoring tasks in fMRI consistently engage the insula and adjacent inferior frontal operculum (Zaki et al., 2012),

regions also active during emotional self-appraisal, suggesting a shared substrate for bodily and affective awareness.

At the network level, recent research indicates widespread dysregulation of functional connectivity. Weber et al. (2025) compared 58 individuals with FND to 58 healthy controls and found that patients entered less frequently a brain state characterized by salience network and default mode network (DMN) co-activation, and more frequently a state of somatomotor–salience co-activation with DMN deactivation. FND participants also showed reduced DMN coupling and increased somatomotor–rTPJ coupling, potentially reflecting diminished flexibility in brain-state switching and altered self-referential processing linked to impaired motor control (Weber et al., 2025).

Interoception in FND

Interoception plays a foundational role in shaping bodily self-awareness, emotion, and agency. In FND, emerging evidence indicates that multiple dimensions of interoceptive processing: accuracy, sensibility, and metacognitive insight, may be disrupted, potentially contributing to core symptoms of altered bodily control and ownership.

However, findings are mixed. Using the Heart Rate Tracking Task to measure interoception, Millman et al. (2023) reported intact interoceptive accuracy but reduced metacognitive insight (confidence in performance) in people with FND, whereas Ricciardi et al. (2021) found the reverse pattern: reduced accuracy but intact insight in FMD. Both studies, however, identified lower interoceptive sensibility, with participants describing discomfort and detachment from bodily sensations. These findings suggest that FND involves disrupted integration between objective bodily signals and subjective awareness.

Heart rate variability (HRV) offers an implicit physiological measure of interoceptive regulation. Several studies report reduced HRV (Ponnusamy et al., 2011; Maurer et al., 2016) and elevated baseline heart rate in FND (Paredes-Echeverri et al., 202), consistent with chronic autonomic hyperarousal and impaired parasympathetic flexibility. Although the direction of causality is uncertain-whether stress dysregulation causes FND or results from it, the evidence points toward sustained autonomic–interoceptive imbalance (Maurer et al., 2016; Porges, 1992).

Using a respiratory resistance sensitivity task, Stoffel et al. (2025), found that participants with FND had reduced respiratory interoceptive sensitivity (i.e., lower ability to detect subtle airway resistance changes), and that this was negatively correlated with somatoform dissociation severity. A task-based fMRI study by Sojka et al. (2025) demonstrated that during a heartbeat-attention task, FND patients showed decreased activation in right anterior insula and dorsal anterior cingulate cortex compared with healthy controls. These activations correlated with interoceptive accuracy, implicating key interoceptive network hubs impaired in FND.

These findings imply that in FND:

- Interoceptive sensibility and bodily self-trust may be compromised (even if raw accuracy is variable).
- Neural circuitry for interoception (insula, cingulate, salience network) may be less responsive or less well-integrated.
- Dysfunction in interoception correlates with symptom severity, dissociation and altered agency.

Mechanistically, disrupted interoception may contribute to symptom generation by altering predictive models of bodily state and action (Seth, 2013; Edwards et al., 2012). Therefore, therapeutically, targeting interoceptive awareness could help restore body ownership, agency, and emotion regulation in FND. Specifically, techniques such as interoceptive training, mindfulness, biofeedback and fasting may have potential to recalibrate predictive models and improve symptoms, though evidence in FND is preliminary.

XR and FND

Extended reality is an umbrella term used to describe: Virtual Reality (completely virtual visual experiences), Augmented Reality (virtual elements transposed over non-virtual elements) and Mixed Reality (virtual elements interacting with non-virtual elements). In neuropsychiatric research, VR has been used to deliver exposure therapy, by simulating triggering scenarios accessibly and safely - under the guidance of a therapist. VR also has been explored in gamified physiotherapy for motor rehabilitation and as a means to record performances of tasks under modified parameters in order to better understand pathological mechanisms (Freeman et al., 2017).

In the context of Functional Neurological Disorder (FND), extended reality (XR) offers a uniquely powerful framework to explore the interaction between perception, prediction, and voluntary movement. A recent systematic review by Brouwer et al. (2024) identified twelve studies employing virtual reality (VR) in FND, most of which focused on modulating the sense of agency in functional motor disorder (FMD) or developing physiotherapeutic and vestibular paradigms for persistent postural-perceptual dizziness (PPPD).

Mechanistic studies, such as those by Nahab et al. (2017), demonstrated that VR-based manipulations of visuomotor synchrony can reveal altered activation of the right dorsolateral prefrontal cortex and pre-supplementary motor area in FMD, supporting predictive processing models of disrupted agency. Gandolfi et al. (2021) further showed that immersive VR environments can modulate postural control under attention-demanding conditions, while Nguyen et al. (2019) and Bullock et al. (2022) reported promising feasibility for integrating VR into motor rehabilitation via exposure-based mirror visual feedback therapy.

In PPPD, VR-based balance and desensitisation paradigms have provided mechanistic and clinical insights: Riccelli et al. (2017) and Passamonti et al. (2018) used fMRI with virtual

rollercoasters to link altered vestibulo-visual processing to insular and frontal cortex dysfunction, and Choi et al. (2021) and Yamaguchi et al. (2020) demonstrated symptom and mood improvement following VR-based vestibular training.

Together, these findings highlight XR not only as a therapeutic adjunct, but as an experimental platform to test neurocognitive models of FND, particularly regarding how predictive processing, self-agency and interoceptive inference interact. However, despite growing evidence for XR's relevance to exteroceptive and motor domains, no published studies to date have directly examined XR-based modulation or measurement of interoception in people with FND, representing a critical frontier for future research.

XR and Interoception

Extended reality offers unique affordances that make it well-suited to target interoception. First, XR enables immersive multisensory environments in which internal bodily signals (e.g., heartbeat, breathing, galvanic skin response) can be made visible, audible or tactile to the user, thereby converting otherwise subtle interoceptive cues into salient feedback. For example, using virtual reality 3D lungs synchronized with participants' breathing cycles in real time, Hu et al. have created an immersive visual-auditory exteroception of their breathing, that resulted in a higher pain threshold potentially via augmentation of cortical visual-auditory activations detected in fNIRS (Functional near-infrared spectroscopy) (2021).

Second, XR supports biofeedback and gamification: bodily signals can be fed back into the environment (for instance, controlling avatars or progressing game tasks) so that interoceptive regulation becomes interactive. Studies show that VR biofeedback training can increase heart-rate variability (HRV) (which reflects the body's ability to adjust heart beat to subtle internal changes) and reduce physiological stress responses (Daniel-Watanabe et al., 2024).

Third, XR allows controlled manipulations of sensory input and body representation; for example, synchronising an avatar's breathing or heartbeat with the user's, or introducing visuo-interoceptive conflicts (e.g., avatar breathing faster/slower than user) to probe and train interoceptive awareness and adaptation. Within this context, the Body Ownership Illusion (BOI) provides an important framework for understanding how virtual embodiment influences interoceptive processing. BOI in virtual reality is a widely used paradigm to study body perception and self-representation. The underlying mechanism is thought to involve multisensory integration and the resolution of visuo-tactile or visuo-kinesthetic sensory conflicts, whereby synchronous feedback between visual, tactile, and proprioceptive cues leads the brain to attribute a virtual body or body part as one's own (Czuba & Kowal, 2019; Tsakiris, 2010).

The rubber hand illusion (RHI) demonstrates how synchronous visual and tactile stimulation can cause a person to experience ownership over an external or artificial limb (Ramachandran & Hirstein, 1998). This paradigm illustrates the brain's capacity to update its body representation based on multisensory integration. Importantly, interoceptive signals (such as heartbeat) interact with body ownership. Suzuki et al. (2013) showed that the strength of the rubber hand illusion is

modulated by cardiac signals; participants with higher interoceptive accuracy experienced weaker illusory ownership, highlighting that interoceptive awareness can constrain multisensory-driven body representation. This suggests that VR paradigms integrating BOI with real-time interoceptive feedback can experimentally manipulate and enhance the coherence between internal and external bodily representations. For instance, one VR study found that when a virtual avatar's respiration was changed relative to the participant's own, the participant's respiration rate adjusted accordingly; a demonstration of visuo-interoceptive entrainment (Czub & Kowal, 2019). Such findings highlight how XR can be used to experimentally manipulate interoceptive-exteroceptive congruence, offering a powerful tool for both studying and enhancing interoceptive processes.

Finally, XR environments offer enhanced engagement, repeatability and ecological validity compared to traditional interoceptive training methods (e.g., heartbeat tracking, breathing exercises alone). XR can maintain user motivation, provide immersive narratives or tasks, integrate multimodal feedback (visual, auditory, haptic) and adapt dynamically to the user's responses (González-Erena et al., 2025).

In sum, when XR is used in tandem with biofeedback, it creates a bridge between internal bodily processes (interoception) and external feedback/representations, making it a promising platform both for studying interoception (by manipulating and measuring internal signal processing) and modulating it (by training users to attend to, interpret and regulate their bodily states).

Review of Existing Interoception XR Paradigms

XR technologies have already begun to be used in studies and interventions explicitly targeting interoception. Several paradigms illustrate how XR can be deployed for interoceptive assessment and training:

- VR biofeedback breathing/training: A virtual reality respiratory biofeedback system increased breath awareness, improved diaphragmatic breathing and increased respiratory sinus arrhythmia compared with a no-feedback control (Blum et al., 2019).
- VR game with HRV biofeedback under stress: A VR game training breathing regulation under stress conditions resulted in greater HRV in the trained vs untrained group (Daniel-Watanabe et al., 2025).
- Real-time haptic heartbeat feedback: A study comparing haptic vs visual feedback found that haptic augmentation of heartbeat feedback improved interoceptive accuracy and confidence in healthy adults, compared to visual feedback (Dobrushina et al., 2024).
- Visuo-interoceptive conflict paradigm: In a VR study where a virtual first-person avatar's respiration was manipulated relative to the user's, participants adjusted their breathing rate (entrained) to match the avatar, significantly in terms of both statistical and clinical significance, demonstrating the plasticity of interoceptive control via visuo-interoceptive feedback (Czub & Kowal, 2019).

These examples highlight how XR can be used both to measure interoceptive processing (by manipulating internal–external signal congruence) and to train interoceptive regulation (via immersive feedback loops). XR therefore provides the following advantages for both studying and modulating interoception:

- Real-time multimodal feedback of internal physiological signals.
- Controlled experimental manipulation of internal vs external cues (e.g., altering feedback timing or congruency).
- High engagement and repeatability, which may aid adherence in training.
- Potential to embed interoceptive training into functional tasks, games or immersive environments rather than purely static tasks.

In summary, XR holds strong promise as a tool for interoceptive science and intervention, offering ways to enhance, measure, and manipulate interoceptive processing.

Study (year)	Population	XR modality / paradigm	Biometrics / signal	Key result	Relevance for FND
Czub & Kowal (2019)	Healthy adults	VR breathing avatar (first-person) with manipulated avatar respiration	Respiration rate (respiratory monitor)	Participants adjusted their breathing to match avatar rate (visuo-respiratory entrainment).	Demonstrates that visuo-interoceptive conflict in XR can entrain respiration - useful to test interoceptive updating and prediction error in FND.
Monti et al. (2019)	Healthy volunteers	Immersive VR with avatar breathing synced to participant	Respiration	Matching avatar respiration increases sense of body ownership/agency.	Shows breathing-based XR manipulations can alter body ownership; directly relevant to agency disturbances in FND.

Daniel-Watanabe et al. (2024)	Healthy adults (training RCT)	VR biofeedback game teaching paced-breathing, practiced under stress	HR, HRV, respiration	VR biofeedback increased diaphragmatic breathing and improved HRV under stress vs control.	Proof-of-principle that VR biofeedback can train autonomic regulation (HRV), a targetable interoceptive marker in FND.
Pratviel et al. (2024)	Clinical / non-clinical mixed samples	Relaxing VR nature immersion vs HRV biofeedback outside VR	HRV, anxiety/stress measures	VR immersion alone produced similar reductions in stress/anxiety as HRV biofeedback outside VR.	Suggests VR alone (without explicit biofeedback) can modulate autonomic tone: relevant for designing lower-burden XR interventions for FND.
Dobrushina et al. (2024)	Healthy adults, randomized	Real-time haptic heartbeat feedback vs visual heartbeat feedback	ECG to synchronise haptic heartbeat timing	Single session of haptic feedback improved interoceptive accuracy and confidence; visual feedback did not.	Indicates modality (haptic > visual) matters - informs XR design for FND (use tactile/affective channels to boost bodily trust).

Hook (2024)	Adults with knee osteoarthritis, chronic pain and kinesioophobia	Mobile VR nature + paced-breathing app with HRV monitoring	HRV, self-reported stress, Multidimensional Assessment of Interoceptive Awareness	Feasible delivery; signals of improved HRV and acceptability.	Practical model for scalable XR-HRV interventions that might be adapted for FND rehabilitation.
Sebri et al. (2023)	Protocol / pilot targeting clinical sample of breast cancer survivors	VR program to promote interoception and emotional wellbeing	HR, self-reported interoception	Protocol describes VR interoception training and outcome measures	Directly relevant framework for applying XR interoceptive training in clinical populations.
Orgil et al. (2024)	Pediatric patients undergoing procedures	Biofeedback-based VR (HRV)	HR, HRV, feasibility metrics	Feasible, acceptable; HRV improvements during sessions.	Shows viability of HRV biofeedback VR in clinical populations - supports feasibility for FND cohorts with appropriate adaptation.

Table 1: Summary of literature findings on XR and Interoception.

Interoception in XR and FND

Bringing together interoception, XR, and Functional Neurological Disorder (FND) opens compelling avenues for both research and intervention. Interoceptive dysfunction is implicated in FND, and XR provides an innovative platform to translate internal bodily processes into perceivable, interactive experiences. Through immersive, adjustable feedback loops, XR could allow individuals to observe, feel, and regulate their internal states in real time, directly engaging bodily self-processing networks (such as the insula, temporoparietal junction, and salience/sensorimotor networks) that appear disrupted in FND.

Virtual Reality (VR) has shown preliminary promise in exposure and embodiment-based interventions, providing controlled environments for safe re-exposure to triggering sensations and contexts. Embodied VR, where participants inhabit a first-person avatar, can align visual feedback with physiological rhythms such as heartbeats or breathing, potentially training attentional focus on interoceptive cues. Augmented Reality (AR) and Mixed Reality (MR) extend this potential by overlaying biofeedback directly onto the user's body, deepening self-recognition and enhancing the sense of ownership over interoceptive sensations - processes often altered in FND.

Mechanistic research potential

XR offers a way to experimentally probe the interoceptive disturbances found in FND. For example, one might design a VR task in which participants with FND experience the perspective of an avatar whose heart-rate or breathing is synced (or unsynced) with their own bodily rhythm, thereby systematically manipulating interoceptive prediction errors. The response of FND participants (behavioural, physiological, neural) could reveal whether their interoceptive updating is atypical vs controls. This could deepen mechanistic understanding of how interoception relates to symptoms, agency and network dysfunction in FND.

Therapeutic clinical potential

XR-based interoceptive training could be adapted for FND populations. For example, a VR biofeedback game where users see their HRV visualised, are rewarded for modulating it (via slow breathing, body awareness tasks) and gradually integrate these skills into embodied tasks (e.g., virtual movement, posture tasks) might strengthen interoceptive awareness, reduce dissociation and improve bodily trust. Given preliminary findings that interoceptive awareness training (e.g., "Body Signal Integration" training) is feasible and acceptable in FND (Panchmatia et al., 2025), XR could enhance these protocols.

Potential Issues

To apply XR to FND-interoception interventions requires attention to several issues:

- Usability in FND populations (e.g., motor symptoms, fatigue, dissociation) must be assessed; one preliminary XR biofeedback study in motor FND, by Dutta et al. (2025) found mixed usability depending on the type of VR task. Notably their 'position feedback' task - involving arm movements to interact with virtual objects - scored an "excellent" usability score, whereas the relaxation and a haptic resistance tasks received mixed feedback.

- Longitudinal efficacy: do XR interoceptive gains transfer to daily life and reduce FND symptoms? Currently no published RCTs in FND have been found for this specific approach.
- Ethical and safety issues: for FND patients who may have heightened dissociation or bodily alienation, immersive XR could potentially trigger undesirable effects (e.g., depersonalisation) - so protocols need supervision and safety design.
- Tailoring biofeedback to interoceptive dimensions: Different people with FND may show differing patterns (accuracy vs insight vs sensibility), as Millman et al. (2023) have found heterogeneity in interoceptive profiles in FND. Therefore, XR training may need to target specific deficits rather than one-size-fits-all.

XR-based interoception interventions hold strong theoretical promise for FND: by directly engaging the bodily self-processing networks that appear disrupted in FND (insula, TPJ, salience/sensorimotor networks) via immersive, adjustable feedback loops, XR could support both mechanistic investigation and novel therapeutic pathways. However, significant empirical work remains to establish efficacy, safety and generalisability in FND populations.

Proposed Directions for Future Research

A proposed conceptual pathway for future research and intervention could begin with assessment, using XR tasks to measure interoceptive accuracy, sensibility, and insight in individuals with FND compared to healthy controls under embodied, multisensory conditions such as visuo-interoceptive conflicts. Building on this, training could employ XR biofeedback games that target HRV, breathing, heartbeat, and body awareness through integrated visual, haptic, and movement-based feedback, fostering active engagement with bodily signals. The next stage could involve combining XR-based interoceptive training with established rehabilitative approaches such as physiotherapy or cognitive-behavioural therapy (CBT), thereby translating interoceptive improvements into enhanced agency, symptom reduction, and restored motor control. Finally, outcomes should be evaluated across multiple dimensions; not only interoceptive measures (accuracy, insight, sensibility), but also symptom severity, motor performance, autonomic regulation (e.g., HRV), and subjective bodily self-trust, to capture both mechanistic and functional benefits.

Gamification and Flow-Based Engagement

Speculatively, gamification provides a powerful mechanism for sustaining engagement and reinforcing positive interoceptive learning. Heart rate and HRV feedback can be incorporated into interactive experiences where maintaining physiological coherence (e.g., steady HRV or calm breathing) is rewarded through environmental changes, narrative progress, or aesthetic reinforcement.

This could create positive feedback loops that align physiological regulation with pleasure and play- potentially countering the discomfort and avoidance often seen in FND. In predictive

processing terms, play may help reprogram maladaptive high-level priors by safely exploring new body–mind contingencies. Games designed around “flow state” principles (Csikszentmihalyi, 1990) could also enhance attentional stability, embodiment, and emotional regulation.

For example, rhythm- or dance-based XR games could integrate biometric tracking and internal visualizations. Users might move in synchrony with their heartbeat or breath, gradually improving interoceptive accuracy and autonomic flexibility. More meditative MR experiences could use the same framework to guide stillness, gentle movement, or mindful focus.

Dance and Embodied Practices in XR

Integrating insights from Dance Movement Therapy (DMT) and Ecstatic Dance into XR may further enhance interoceptive training. Both approaches emphasize body awareness, nonverbal communication, and self-expression, which are particularly relevant to FND’s disruptions in body agency and somatic confidence.

Dance-based interventions have demonstrated benefits across neurological and psychiatric populations (including Parkinson’s disease, dementia, and depression) with reported improvements in motor coordination, cognitive function, and emotional wellbeing (Lossing et al., 2017; Zuliani et al., 2023). DMT specifically prioritizes reconnecting with internal sensations (Lauffenburger, 2020; Powers, 2024), while Ecstatic Dance has been associated with increased interoceptive awareness and social connectedness (Forest, 2022).

XR could adapt these practices for FND-friendly formats, combining rhythm, movement, and biofeedback. For instance, an MR “body listening” game might guide users to direct attention toward different bodily regions through gaze or touch, using rhythmic cues and visual effects to foster self-agency and interoceptive curiosity rather than avoidance.

Mechanistic and Clinical Research Proposals

A mechanistic line of investigation could employ a mechanistic VR or MR Visuo-Cardiac Conflict Task to assess interoceptive updating and agency in people with FND versus matched controls. Participants could view their avatar’s visible heartbeat that is (a) synchronous, (b) delayed, or (c) exaggerated. Measurements could be taken of ECG, HRV, heartbeat discrimination, agency rating; to measure interoceptive accuracy, heartbeat matching tendency with the avatar and altered sense of agency across different conditions and in comparison to healthy controls. It is hypothesised that individuals with FND may exhibit reduced sensitivity to cardiac synchrony and greater agency disruption when exposed to conflicting interoceptive feedback.

A therapeutic line of investigation could be a randomized control trial of XR HRV Biofeedback + Physiotherapy, to test whether XR biofeedback enhances interoceptive sensibility and motor outcomes. Over the span of several weeks, participants would engage in an immersive, gamified training paradigm in which heart-rate variability dynamically modulates aspects of the

virtual environment, reinforcing interoceptive regulation during physical rehabilitation. The primary objective would be to evaluate feasibility and whether XR-enhanced physiotherapy supports improvements in interoceptive sensibility, HRV, and functional outcomes relative to standard care.

Additionally, a personalised haptic heartbeat XR training could serve as a proof-of-concept intervention targeting interoceptive confidence, or “bodily trust,” in people with FND. Using haptic or vibrotactile feedback aligned with real-time cardiac signals, the program would provide embodied biofeedback designed to strengthen awareness of internal bodily rhythms within a supportive virtual context. Improvements in interoceptive accuracy, confidence, emotional awareness, and symptom severity could be assessed pre- and post-intervention to evaluate preliminary efficacy.

Conclusion

Extended reality (XR) provides an unprecedented opportunity to study and modulate interoception within functional neurological disorder (FND). By rendering internal bodily processes perceptible and interactive, XR allows researchers and clinicians to directly engage the mechanisms that underlie altered bodily awareness, agency, and emotion regulation in FND. Through controlled visuo-interoceptive manipulations, biofeedback, and embodied virtual experiences, XR can operationalise theoretical models of predictive processing and test how interoceptive prediction errors contribute to symptom generation. Simultaneously, XR’s immersive and adaptive feedback systems offer a novel therapeutic route for recalibrating interoceptive awareness and bodily trust.

Nevertheless, important limitations remain. Most existing XR–interoception studies have been conducted in healthy populations, and evidence for transfer to clinical improvement in FND is preliminary. Usability and safety considerations, particularly for individuals prone to dissociation or fatigue, require careful evaluation. Moreover, interoception itself is multidimensional, encompassing accuracy, sensibility, and metacognitive insight; future XR interventions must be tailored to these distinct components rather than adopting uniform protocols. Methodological challenges also persist in isolating interoceptive from exteroceptive effects within immersive environments, and in translating short-term physiological changes (e.g., increased HRV) into lasting symptom relief or improved agency.

Despite these caveats, XR represents a uniquely integrative platform linking perception, prediction and embodiment in a way few other tools can. Its ability to visualise and modulate the dynamic interplay between brain, body, and self positions it as a promising medium for both mechanistic research and patient-centred intervention. For FND, where traditional boundaries between neurology and psychiatry have long obscured the embodied dimensions of experience, XR could help reimagine treatment as an active dialogue between the mind’s expectations and the body’s lived reality.

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